

Perceptions of Palestinian Students towards Using Audio Visual Aids in the English Language Classroom at the University Level*

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Abstract

Learning English can be a complex process for students in general mainly because learning a new language requires acquiring and mastering different language skills. However, this process can be simplified through implementing useful methods in the EFL classroom. Based on this, the present study investigated the students' perceptions towards using interesting resources like audio visual aids in the Palestinian context. A qualitative analysis method was used to address the research questions. Data was collected by means of semi-structured interviews. Throughout the course of 21 semi-structured interviews, students expressed their positive attitudes towards using audio visual aids, mainly videos and pictures in their EFL classrooms. Students emphasized that such materials were useful in different ways, especially in improving language knowledge, enhancing the clarity of the taught material, providing variety in learning, retaining information, developing language competence and managing time. Students recommended more exposure to audio visual aids in the language classroom due to their various benefits.

دراسة حول تصورات الطلبة بما يتعلق باستخدام الوسائل السمعية البصرية في حصة اللغة الإنجليزية على المستوى الجامعي.

ملخص:

قد يكون تعلم اللغة الانجليزية عملية معقدة للطلبة، حيث أن تعلم لغة جديدة يتطلب أن يكتسب الطلبة مهارات لغوية مختلفة. إلا أنه يمكن تبسيط هذه العملية من خلال تطبيق أساليب مفيدة في الحصص الدراسية لمساعدة الطلبة. وبالتالي، فقد بحثت الدراسة الحالية تصورات الطلبة نحو استخدام مواد مفيدة وفعالة مثل الوسائل السمعية البصرية. تم استخدام طريقة التحليل الكيفي للإجابة عن أسئلة الدراسة. وتم جمع البيانات عن طريق المقابلات شبه المنظمة من خلال مقابلة 21 طالباً. أعرب الطلبة المشاركون عن مواقفهم الإيجابية تجاه استخدام المواد السمعية البصرية وبالأخص الفيديو

والصور في الحصص الدراسية للغة الانجليزية. لقد أكد الطلبة الذين تمت مقابلتهم أن تلك المواد مفيدة جداً وخاصة في: تحسين المعرفة اللغوية، وتعزيز وضوح المواد التعليمية، وتوفير التنوع في التعلم، وتذكر المعلومات، وتطوير اللغة وإدارة الوقت. أخيراً، أوصى الطلبة بضرورة استخدام المزيد من الوسائل السمعية البصرية في حصص اللغة الانجليزية بسبب فوائدها المتعددة.

الكلمات المفتاحية: الوسائل السمعية البصرية، اللغة الإنجليزية كلغة أجنبية، التعليم، التعلم، غرفة الصف، الطريقة المباشرة، الطريقة الصامتة.

Introduction

Learning a new language can be quite hindering to students; this is mainly due to the fact that language learning can be somewhat complex since it requires mastering the four language skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. In order to solve this issue and simplify the process of language learning, teachers must pursue several methods to make it easier for students to master these language skills. One useful method is using audio visual aids in the EFL classroom. For instance, it is well-known that "video allows us to introduce any aspect of real life in the language learning environment, and contextualize the learning process" (Sherman, 2003). Thus, students benefit greatly from video material on different levels. It is also obvious that "students of all levels can benefit from the use of video" retrieved from "learning vocabulary through authentic video and subtitles". Most significantly, "it has become a common phenomenon to integrate language textbooks with audio and video as additional or supplementary resources for classroom language learning activities" (Mathew & Alidmat, 2013).

Recently, Birzeit University (Palestine) has used Cambridge unlock textbooks where audio visuals are integrated within the learning material (both in the listening and reading text books). Hence, they have become applicable to learners from different levels.

Based on this, the current study explores the students' perceptions towards using audio visual aids in the EFL classroom at Birzeit University (Palestine). The study addresses the following questions:

1. What are the Palestinian students' perceptions regarding using audio visual aids in the EFL classroom at the university level?
2. What are the Palestinian students' perceptions regarding the benefits of audio visual aids in the EFL classroom at the university level?

Theoretical Background:

Language learning theories have affirmed that the development of language learning contains three main components: language input (reading and listening), assimilation (internal processing and memorization) and language output (speaking, writing and translation) (Wang, 2015). It has been indicated that "the process of viewing video materials in the classroom is a combination of language input and assimilation" (Wang, 2015, P.24). Throughout the years, visuals have been utilized in language classrooms. Perhaps, "the Direct Approach was the first to give importance to the use of visuals in the language classroom in the 1920s and 1930s" (García, 2013, P.9). Furthermore, using tape recordings and picture slides were of a special importance in the 1950s-1960s with the introduction of the Audio-lingual method in the USA. García (2013) has also addressed that issue based upon behaviorists' theories which offered students with models to emulate native speakers. Moreover, other approaches have focused on exposing learners to real life situations through using various types of visual aids. For instance, the Oral-Situational Approach has emphasized learning language situationally. Tangible objects, pictures, realia, charts and flashcards were widely used in the classroom to promote real life contexts (García, 2013). Students were also taught throughout a mixture of textbooks, filmstrips, tape-recordings, slides and classroom presentation in the 1960s as the Audio-Visual Method was developed by French scholars (García, 2013).

Other approaches have also made use of visuals throughout history in ways that would help avoiding the use of L1 in the language classroom. One of those is the Silent Way. This approach has a very consistent classroom procedure; first, sounds are taught, next are words and afterwards sentences throughout coloured rods of different shapes, which have been previously associated to the diverse linguistic items (Molina, Cañado & Agulló, n.d). Additionally, the Natural Approach considers language as communication. It designates that logical input is offered by using visual and kinesthetic aids, and students are not asked to produce output

immediately, as they usually go through a silent period (Molina, Cañado & Agulló, n.d). In addition, audio visual aids provide a rich environment for acquiring language. Asher (1977) focused on several characteristics of first language acquisition. First, children have to be exposed to immense amount of input before they learn how to speak (Asher, 1977 as cited in Molina, Cañado & Agulló). Second children gain input wherein a lot of physical manipulation and action is exerted (Nunan, 1991 as cited in Molina, Cañado & Agulló). Gezezin (2014) has also addressed the importance of video as a form of visual aids in language teaching. The researchers have indicated that this importance has been highlighted and has gained much weight with the increase in communicative language teaching theories around the world. Visuals can maintain the input that the students receive. In the Cognitive Approach to second language learning, a lot of importance has been given to target language input. Linguistic meaning is based on experience and use, and so students should be placed in an environment that activates their experiences and allows them to use the language for real purposes (Molina, Cañado & Agulló, n.d).

Finally, Sherman (2003) discussed the significance of using videos in the language classroom. According to her, there is a wide variety of video recordings such as drama video (films, soap operas, sitcoms, etc.), documentaries, TV news and weather, discussions, interviews, TV commercials, sports programs, talk shows, game shows and educational films. This could be utilized in different ways and in a wide scope so that students will benefit from them in the classroom.

Significance of the Study:

The study aimed at promoting the use of audio visual aids especially visuals in the EFL classroom at the university level in Palestine. It has created a successful model for learning at Birzeit University. This in turn contributes to the society in different ways as it encourages teachers to use more technology in their classrooms. It also opens the window for new techniques and enables them to focus their teaching on achieving the target learning objectives with less effort and time.

Additionally, using these aids will provide a rich, educational, interactive setting for students. This helps them become heavily engaged in the process of learning. As the proverb says "One seeing is worth one thousand hearings".

Research Design and Methodology:

The subjects of the study were composed of 91 students. They were all undergraduate students at Birzeit University. Overall, 21 students were interviewed for the study. The sample could be considered a "Convenience Sample" (i.e. Select whoever is easiest, closest, etc. (Patton & Cochran, 2002). All students were taught by the researchers. They were Arabic native speakers and they were from various majors as well. Students were taught through the Cambridge Unlock textbooks (level B2.1, ENGC 2203). It is a 2-credit hour course that focuses on effective argument. At this level, students are able to account for and sustain their opinions in discussions by providing relevant explanations, arguments and comments. Students were able to understand the main ideas of complex texts on both concrete and abstract topics, including technical discussions in their field of specialization, interact with a degree of fluency and spontaneity that makes regular interaction with native speakers quite possible without strain for either party. They were also able to produce clear, detailed text on a wide range of subjects and explain a viewpoint on a topical issue giving the advantages and disadvantages of various options (see <http://www.birzeit.edu/en>). The textbooks are integrated with audio visuals (mostly documentaries that are related to the topics in the course material). Each unit in the book contains an educational video that represents the theme of the unit. Students were informed that their responses are meant for research purposes. The study was conducted over the summer of the year 2016-2017. As the study investigated the use of audio visuals (particularly videos, pictures and captions) in the classroom, it was important to look into the students' responses towards using audiovisuals in the classroom and examine their usefulness. In order to answer the first research question, the researchers asked the students the following questions during the face-to-face interviews:

1. Do you find a need for the English teachers to use audio visual aids in the classroom?
2. If yes, why do they need to use audio visual aids in the classroom?
3. If no, why do you think they should not use audio visual aids in the classroom?
4. Are audio visual aids used in the English Language classroom? Yes/no
5. If yes, are they related to your lesson?

As for the second research question, the researchers asked them the following:

1. Do you find the audio visual aids useful?
2. If yes, how?
3. If no, why?
4. Your suggestions about audio visual aids in the English language classroom.

A qualitative analysis method was used to address the research questions. Data was collected by means of semi-structured interviews. In semi-structured interviews, everyone receives the same questions, but there is flexibility in how they are asked. It is mainly useful for exploring the views of a person towards something (Teijlingen, 2014). The students were asked ten questions related to the use of audio visual aids in their English language classes. Their answers were voice-recorded via a smartphone, transcribed and analyzed later on. Most of the questions were open-ended and students were asked to express their views objectively. The questions were adopted from an online study published by Mathew & Alidmat (2013) in the international journal of higher education. Thematic analysis of the data was also utilized as a sort of qualitative method. A thematic analysis looks across all the data to recognize the common issues that reappear, and identify the main themes that summarize all the collected views (Patton & Cochran, P.23). Thematic analysis is a technique for recognizing, analyzing, and reporting themes in data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Moreover, a theme captures something important about the data in relation to the research question, and represents some level of patterned response or meaning within the data set" (Braun & Clarke, 2006). In this form of analysis, a number of topics, themes or issues were discussed based upon the face-to-face interviews that were carried out through the present study (Mason, 2002).

Literature Review:

➤ The Various Positive Effects of Utilizing Audio Visual Aids in the Language Classrooms.

The benefits of video materials in EFL instruction, on account of developing a framework of teaching values, strategies and guidelines for using video materials was discussed by Zhaogang Wang, in an attempt to facilitate EFL instruction for non-English majors. The study specifically investigated

the aim of utilizing video material in EFL classrooms and the usefulness of such material as well.

There are certain reasons why teachers use multimedia audio visual aids in the classroom. Garcia (2013) emphasized that visual aids should be integrated in the language classroom due to their positive effects on students. Results of her study were measured both qualitatively and quantitatively. They revealed that teachers do not use audiovisuals as an essential part of the lesson mainly because of time limitation. Of course, students are not satisfied by this.

In a different study, Gezegin (2014) investigated whether there is a significant difference between teaching vocabulary with

audio and teaching vocabulary with video. Gezegin also investigated the students' preferences in terms of learning vocabulary with video versus audio. The study included 50 Turkish university students who were enrolled in intensive English classes at the department of Arts and Science at Amasya University in Turkey. The study used both the qualitative and quantitative methods in analyzing the data. It revealed that employing video might lead to better vocabulary learning in language classrooms when compared to the use of audio material only.

Mathew and Alidmat (2013) indicated that using audio visuals improves the learning environment and stimulates thinking. The researchers indicated that the efficient use of audio visual aids reduces boring learning environments. Their findings suggest that students find audio visual sessions useful and relevant when they have some direct relation to the course content. The study gave insights on the students' perception and opinions on the use of audio visual aids.

In another study, it was confirmed that subtitles can be used with authentic video to improve vocabulary and word recognition as well as vocabulary acquisition skills in EFL classrooms. This will provide authentic input through the written text, oral text and images that will, in turn, contribute to offer a better and longer mental representation of old and new lexical items "Learning Vocabulary through Authentic Video And Subtitles".

Bajramia and Ismailia (2016) looked into authenticity and student motivation and the possibility of incorporating and improving them through using video materials in an EFL classroom. The study investigated the benefits that the language

teachers and learners get in using audio visual aids in teaching and learning the English language. Generally, students find using video material to be interesting, relevant, beneficial and somewhat motivating in class.

➤ **Teachers' Attitudes Towards the Use of Audio Visual Material in the Language Classrooms.**

Omid and Azam (2016) examined Iranian EFL teachers' thoughts and attitudes towards the use of authentic materials at high school level in Iran according to communicative language principles. The study focused on both reading and listening skills. Fifty-seven female and male English teachers participated in the study. A questionnaire has been completed for the purpose of this study. Results were analyzed in terms of frequency and percentage by means of SPSS. The results revealed that English teachers have a positive attitude towards presenting authentic materials in the classroom.

➤ **Using More Visual Aids in the Language Classroom.**

A Case Study by María (2012) at Margarita Salas Secondary School (Majadahonda) examined the use of visual aids in the language classroom. It examined the reasons why teachers (particularly at Margarita Salas high school) use them rarely. It proved that visual aids must be integrated in the language classroom. This is due to the special effects they have on students. The results were measured with qualitative and quantitative methods. They showed that teachers do not use visual aids as part of the everyday lesson because of the timing issues, and students are not content with this matter. The study recommended that the use of multimedia visuals as tools in the language classroom is extremely helpful for students and improves the learning process. Therefore, they should be included in the lessons.

➤ **The Effects of Videos on Students' Language Skills.**

According to Ismaili (2013), videos help enhance students' listening and communication skills. His study's sample included two groups: an experimental and a

control group. It was carried out at the South East European University in the academic year 2011/2012. The participants were pre-intermediate and intermediate level students. The results of the

study showed that there are significant differences between experimental and control group of students concerning integrated skills. The study revealed that movies draw students' attention and present language in a more normal mode. Moreover, movies offer a visual setting which helps students understand and expand their learning skills.

Hamdan (2015) explored the EFL Saudi university students' perceptions of the effect of video material on their listening skills. The study sample consisted of 18 students. It used both qualitative and quantitative analysis. The results of quantitative analysis indicated that there were significant differences in the subjects' perceptions of integrating videos and audios to learn listening skill, in favor of videos utilization. The qualitative analysis revealed that students are more interested in learning through videos rather than audios.

➤ **Benefits of Using Audio Visual Aids for Teachers and Students**

There are advantages for both teachers and learners when using audio visual aids in English language teaching (al-Mamun, 2014). In his study, al-Mamun used a qualitative method to collect data. It was found that the use of audio visual aids helps both the teacher and the learners in teaching and learning language skills.

➤ **Effects of Audio Visual Aids on Teaching English Active Vocabulary to EFL Learners.**

Sabrina (2015) tried to investigate the effects of audio visual aids on teaching English vocabulary to EFL learners. The aim was to explore if audio visual aids can help learners utilize their active vocabulary. It also explored teachers' attitude towards these aids. The researcher adopted a descriptive method that depends on two means of research: a questionnaire and classroom observation. Results clearly indicated that both teachers and students support teaching and learning using audio visual aids in the classroom. Nevertheless, the lack of such material negatively affects students' willingness to learn English vocabulary actively. Moreover, students showed a lot of excitement towards watching authentic materials and audio visuals, to improve their speaking ability.

Findings and Analysis:

This section reveals the themes that resulted from the interviews' transcription. After looking into

the interviewees' responses thoroughly, the students' perceptions towards using audio visuals and their benefits were summarized into the bellow mentioned main themes and subthemes.

First, improving language knowledge: audio visual aids provide assistance in learning new vocabulary, audio visual aids provide experience and fluency in English, audio visuals provide background information, audio visual aids assist in thinking and gaining knowledge.

Second, enhancing the clarity of taught material: audio visual aids increase the ability to imagine sounds and get ideas, audio visual aids help enhance the students' ability to focus and attract their attention.

Third, audio visual aids provide variety in learning: audio visual aids help break the routine and move away from the traditional modes of leaning, audio visual aids provide a motivating environment for the students to learn, audio visual aids expose students to other cultures, audio visual aids provide variety in teaching methodologies.

Fourth, retaining information: audio visual aids enhance the ability to understand, audio visual aids enhance the ability to retain information.

Fifth, developing language: audio visual aids help in enhancing the language development. They help in enhancing the students' various skills, especially the listening and speaking skills, audio visual aids improve the language accent, and help increase students' participation and confidence in the classroom.

Sixth, managing time: audio visual aids save time and effort in passing the information to students.

Thematic Analysis:

During the course of 21 semi-structured interviews, participants expressed their attitudes towards using audio visual aids, mainly videos in their EFL classrooms and whether they think using them is useful. Generally, participants revealed positive attitudes towards using audio visual aids in the English classroom. They have also revealed affirmative attitudes towards the usefulness of using the audio visual aids in their classrooms. The following sections summarize the students' responses

to the face-to-face interview questions and the main themes and subthemes that have emerged from analyzing the interviews' transcription of all the interview questions.

1. Improving language knowledge.

1.1 Audio visual aids provide assistance in learning new vocabulary.

Three students talked about the importance of using audio visual aids in the English language classroom in terms of helping in vocabulary development. One student stated, "It is useful. First, the language development and when you listen to the speaker, you can take new words and vocabulary". Another added, "It is useful for students to help us to understand the meaning". A third added, "To give vocabulary to the student and train his ear".

1.2 Audio visual aids provide experience and fluency in English.

It was clear throughout the students' responses that audio visual aids provided them with experience and fluency as one student said, "They take from this audio visuals the experience and fluency in English". The same student added, "When I see this video, I see and imagine sounds and this gives me ideas and that is it".

1.3 Audio visual aids offer background information.

In this regard, eight students expressed that being exposed to audio visual aids (mainly videos) in the English classroom helps them trigger their understanding and knowledge in the language. One student stated, "It gives us general information about what we are going to study in the book." Another student pointed that it helps them "To get a full idea about what we are talking about", a third student reported that "They give us as I said a good background about the lesson." "They give the students a general idea about the unit, and helps them prepare well," another student said. It also "Makes the students have a background about the subjects and the students will be more active and more interested," as expressed by another student. Finally, a different student said, "These videos help students to understand the topic of the units and also how to brainstorm, to think about ideas."

1.4 Audio visual aids assist in thinking and gaining knowledge.

Two students added that being exposed to audio visual aids would help them "Make the idea closer" as one student reported. Another student also indicated that it would help "To get a full idea about what we are talking about and help us to think more positive. To get more idea, more information about what we study".

2. Enhancing clarity of taught material.

2.1 Audio visual aids increase the ability to imagine sounds and get ideas.

In a different manner, two students expressed that watching a video as a major form of audio visual aid in their classroom would help them imagine and gain more ideas. One student said, "When I see this video, I see and imagine sounds and this gives me ideas and that is it." Another student stated, "You watch a video; you can imagine what the teacher is talking about in the class."

2.2 Audio visual aids help enhance the students' ability to focus and attract their attention.

Six students reported that using audio visual aids in their English classroom helps them focus. One student said, "It helps our minds focused and all the material can still be in my mind". Another one reported, "We are now in a world of technology, so we are going to be focused when we watch. Maybe 'Eyes can be better than ears'". As another student pointed, "We should use the audio visuals because it helps the students to be more concentrating in the class and it will attract their attention". "It helps to grab the attention of the students" as another student reported. A different student also stated, "It is a good idea for the teachers to get the audio visuals to the class in order to get the classroom attention."

3. Providing variety in learning.

3.1 Audio visual aids help in breaking the routine, moving away from the traditional modes of leaning.

Five students described that using audio visuals in the classroom helps break the traditional classroom routine. In this regard, a student reported, "Maybe it can be fun for the students. It is a different

way. It is different from the usual.” Another student added, “It helps break the routine”. It also “Let us listen to the language and see the spelling and to see them is a good idea not just to read and use the traditional ways” as stated by another student. A different student also reported that, “If they are going to play or they are bored from just talking, they can see something or they can hear something in a different way.”

3.2 Audio visual aids provide a motivating environment for the students to learn.

In this regard, four students expressed that utilizing audio visuals in the classrooms would help motivate them and this would encourage their learning. One student stated, “It is useful for sure because it makes the students more excited to study the lesson.” Another student mentioned, “It makes the class more fun so they can learn in more suitable environment in the class.” A different student reported, “This will make the class more interesting”. The same student also said, “We use it for Cambridge videos so they related to our lesson. This makes the class more interesting and we enjoy when we watching it.”

3.3 Audio visual aids get students exposed to other cultures.

One student stated that audio visual aids “Make us know about other cultures. Some people who are professional in something; to know about other cultures. Maybe we can learn some skills and information.”

3.4 Audio visual aids provide variety in teaching methodology.

Two students indicated that using audio visuals in the language classroom helped them become exposed to various teaching methods. This helped them “To have something new to work with and get different way of getting information. It is very useful” as one student reported. Another student stated that “If we just take a lesson about something, if I just watch it in the class, I will understand more than just to read about it, so we just have more than a way to learn information. This will become more useful.”

4. Retaining information.

4.1 Audio visual aids enhance the ability to understand.

Four students indicated that using audio visuals helped them to understand. A student noted that, “We understand the lesson more.” In the same manner, a student pointed that, “It helps people to understand the unit and it is really connected with the lessons in the book.” Additionally, another student reported that, “It makes the idea clear to the student and to understand what the point of it.” The same student added, “It makes the student understand more about the subject that he study. Maybe when he see and hear, it is better.” Finally, another student pointed that, “We are now in the world of technology and of course we are going to understand when we are watching. Yea, if we just take a lesson about something, if I just watch it in the class, I will understand more than just to read about it.”

4.2 Audio visual aids enhance the ability to retain information.

Two students also said that it helped them remember and retain information. It is “Actually useful because it helps the person to remember the information more than when you speak it. In the video, when I see the idea, I remember it more when I read it.” as one student said. Another noted that, “When I watch the audio visuals it will stick in my mind and I will remember it when I do the exams or tests.”

5. Developing language.

5.1 Audio visual aids help in enhancing the language development. They help enhance the students’ various skills especially the listening and speaking skills.

Seven students stated that it was important for them to be exposed to audio visual aids in the classroom because “It helps students to improve their listening skill and pay attention to the class more than the material. It is more interesting.” as one student reported. Another student noted that it was important to use audio visual aids in the class “To help us listen more to English speaking in order to develop our speaking.” As stated by another student, “It is a good way to improve the listening skills of students.” The same student also added, “For me it improves my skills in listening. By watching things, the listening is more useful. It improves my listening skills.” “They also improve their skills of speaking and conversation with others,” a different student added. “It developed my skills in listening and to talk to have the spelling and build my skills”, another student noted.

Generally, as another student stated, "It helps the students to connect the language and the pictures they see. It will strengthen the ability to connect things through language."

5.2 Audio visual aids improve the language accent.

Among the students who were interviewed, two expressed that using audio visual aids in the classroom helped develop their accent. One student noted that, "When we listen to native speakers, you get better language and conversations will be better." The other noted, "When you listen to the speaker, you can take the accent."

5.3 Audio visual aids help increase students' participation and confidence in the classroom.

Three students reported that utilizing audio visual aids increased the students' ability to feel confident in the language classroom and to participate. One student remarked that, "It is very fun for the students to have some move and active things in class and it is easy for them to exactly know about the subject and to be active with it as they are really bored from just talking in the class. They do not have enough space to talk in class and when watching a video it will be as if they are watching a movie or something like that, so silence would not be bad for that purpose." A different student noted that, "This will make the class more interesting and the students will share and participate with teachers." Finally, another student added, "This will make the class more interesting and the students will share and participate with teacher."

6. Managing Time.

6.1 Audio visual aids save time and effort in passing the information to students.

In this regard, a single student noted that using audio visual aids in the classroom helped save the effort in passing information to students. This student noted that, "They are useful, they clear the points that the teacher want them to reach the students."

Discussion:

Through the face-to-face interviews, the researchers asked the students questions in order to reveal their perceptions towards the use of audio visual aids in their English classroom in addition to the benefits of using them.

In general, from analyzing students' responses to the interview questions, it was evident that 20 students out of 21 strongly believed that audio visual aids must be used in their language classrooms. Only one student thought that they should not be used. "I think no; it is not interesting to watch videos like children" the student noted. However, most students positively affirmed their opinions towards utilizing them in their English language classroom. They also indicated that they were already used in their EFL classroom and that they were all related to their lessons. As for their thoughts regarding whether they were useful or not, all students thought that they were useful in different ways, specifically in: improving language knowledge, enhancing clarity of the taught material, providing variety in learning methodologies, retaining information, developing language and managing time. Moreover, the students were very interested in audio visuals and they recommended that it would be much better if they were used more in the language classroom due to their various benefits.

The results of the current study agree with Gezezin's study which found that employing video might lead to better vocabulary learning in language classrooms when compared to the use of audio material only. Findings of the current study also support the views of Bajramia and Ismailia (2016) who have looked into authenticity and student motivation and the possibility of incorporating and improving them through using video materials in an EFL classroom. Moreover, the importance of using audio visual aids in the English language classroom and its positive effects on listening skills were addressed throughout the previous studies. For instance, Omid and Azam (2016) found that students show a lot of excitement and desire towards watching authentic materials and audio visuals as they improve their speaking ability.

Furthermore, using audio visuals as tools in the language classroom is extremely helpful for students and improves the learning process. Therefore, they should be included in the lessons (María, 2012).

In addition, according to Ismaili (2013), videos help enhance students' listening and communication skill. Results of the present study also correspond with Al-Mamun's study (2014) where it found that the use of audio-visual aids helps both the teacher and the learners in teaching and learning language skills.

To conclude, the present study gives insights on the perceptions of students towards the use and

benefits of audio visual aids in the English language classroom. It is important to note that using such resources in the EFL classroom “helps students gain from a resourceful, interesting and learner-centered classroom” (Mathew & Alidmat, 2013).

Conclusion:

Most students’ responses came in congruity with the literature review and the research questions to emphasize the following:

- Using audio visual aids in the classroom sets enriching educational settings that challenge students’ imagination and invite them to positively indulge in the learning process. It makes lessons more interesting through sharing information.
- Using audio visual aids invites learners to think outside the box collectively and individually, learn new things, and adapt new behavior- how to act and react in the context of new language culture.
- Using audio visual aids increases students’ experiences and confidence in using the target language with much fluency and accuracy.
- Using these aids improves learners’ skills in listening and comprehension. Moreover, they improve learner’s pronunciation through imitation and reception.
- Using these aids enables teachers to manage their time properly and effectively as students are in flux to break the routine and helps teachers motivate them to directly join in.
- Using audio visual aids makes students retain much of the information presented and enables them to do well in oral and written tests.
- Using audio visual aids keeps learners more focused as this involves using the senses of both sound and sight.
- Using audio visuals in the class encourages students to visit other websites. This promotes self-learning approach as students learn on their own at any time since the majority have access to the internet and are currently becoming digital natives and skillful in using technology.

Recommendations:

Based on students’ responses, the researchers strongly recommend using audio visual aids in the classroom for their vital role in enhancing the pace of

the learning process, and promoting efficient time use.

The researchers also recommend that further research should be conducted on related topics. Other researchers are encouraged to focus on technology integration into the classroom and observe how technology’s tools enhance learning and turn learners into avid participants. The study also recommends conducting similar studies at the university level, in order to observe the perceptions of teachers towards using audio visual aids in the EFL classroom.

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